

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

RESEARCH OF MECHANICAL PACKER SITTING STABILITY

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ABSTRACT

The analysis of the accidents of operational belts shows that the main reason for the loss of the belt's efficiency is the additional stresses affecting it, as a result of which the belt is longitudinally and transversely disintegrated, the hermeticity of the groove joints is lost, disintegrated, and crushed. Therefore, this should be checked before the packer is released into the well. A load is applied mechanically or hydraulically to the packer to seat it on the belt. It is known that these forces are applied to the packer, as well as to its components, in dynamic rather than static conditions. However, the approaches to extinguishing its shock nature in certain ways are not enough. For this purpose, it is important to fit the packer fasteners in the belt, remove (release) the packer from the well.

Keywords: axial bending, filter zone, packer, pump-compressor pipes, compressive force.

The urgency of the problem. The analysis of the accidents of maintenance pipelines of repair wells shows that the main reason for the loss of operational capacity of the pipeline is the additional stresses affecting it, as a result of which the longitudinal and transverse disintegration of the pipeline, the loss of hermeticity of the groove joints, disintegration, and crushing occur in the pipeline. Therefore, this should be checked before the packer is released into the well. It is known that when the production line is lowered into the drilling well, a visco-elastic condition is formed around it from the rock and cement ring. In order to carry out certain repair works in the filter zone of the wells, when the pump-compressor pipes are connected to the packer, when this zone of the belt is fixed with a packer, an axial bending occurs in the pipes. It can also occur in the belt itself due to the displacement of the belt in the filter zone. In order to ensure the stability of the packer seating in the wells (repair wells), it is necessary to ensure that the packer is released into the well at a low speed.

Purpose of work. After connecting the pump compressor pipes to the packer during the repair work in the wells, create an axial deflection and increase the effectiveness of the preventive works.

Conducting research work. In this article, measures to mitigate the dynamic effect of force depending on the principle of packing packer seating are considered. The nature of the power transfer to the packer has not been sufficiently considered. At this time, in order to carry out the research of the belt barrel, we divide it into 3 parts and examine it in detail:

- 1) the part between the radii of the operational belt;
- 2) The zone of that belt surrounded by cement with the radii in question;
- 3) the section between the radii with the rock belt exciting effect.

So, the load is applied mechanically or hydraulically to the packer to seat it on the belt. It is known that these forces are applied to the packer, as well as to its components, in dynamic rather than static conditions. However, the approaches to extinguishing its shock nature in certain ways are not enough. For this purpose, it is important to have a smooth - "balanced

seating" of the packer in the well (including lowering the packer into the well, seating its fasteners in the belt, removing (liberating) the packer from the well).

In order to carry out certain repair works in the filter zone of the wells, when the pump-compressor pipes are connected to the packer, when this zone of the belt is fixed with a packer, an axial bending occurs in the pipes. It should be noted that it can also occur in the belt itself due to the displacement of the belt in the filter zone (Fig. 1).

When the packer is placed on the belt, the clamping force generated at the moment it rests on the belt

$$N_i = \pi L_{pak} D \tau_0 \quad (1)$$

here L_{pak} is the distance to the place where the packer sits, D_{pak} is the diameter of the pipe where the packer is connected; τ_0 - is the sliding stress of the cement coating behind the belt.

At the place where the packer is seated, the pipes will be subjected to a compressive force Q_{pak} along the axis:

$$Q_{pak} = \Delta Q_\alpha - N_\tau \tau_0 \quad (2)$$

here ΔQ_α - is an additional compressive force arising from the filter zone (from the pressure difference in the layer) and falling on the shoe, filter, belt and packer-tube system:

$$\Delta Q_{ox} = \frac{\pi}{4} \cdot D_{pak}^2 (P_{lay} - P_{filtr}) \quad (3)$$

here P_{lay} - layer pressure; P_{filtr} - pressure in the filter.

To solve the problem, we assume that the pipes have an initial (initial) curvature and the lower end is closed (immobile) with a packer (DÜIST 632-80) (Fig. 1), then the initial conditions can be written as:

$$X = \pm L_{pak}/2 \text{ olanda } \frac{dS_{ey}}{dx} = 0 \quad (4)$$

here $S_{\partial y}$ – the loading time of the pipes is an additional deviation. Then, for our case, we can determine the critical load according to Euler's criterion as follows:

$$P_{kr} = \frac{4\pi^2 EJ}{l_{fil}} \quad (5)$$

here J – is the moment of inertia:

$$J = \frac{\pi d^3 \delta}{8}$$

According to GOST 632-64, bending stresses in pipes arise from additional compressive load:

$$Q_{ox} \prec P_{kr} = \frac{4\pi^2 EJ}{L_{pak}^2} \quad (6)$$

In the initial state, the pipe deflection is determined as follows:

$$S_0 = \frac{f_{\partial y}}{2} \left(1 + \cos \frac{2\pi \cdot x}{l_{filtr}} \right) \quad (7)$$

If the bent pipes are subjected to compressive forces, the differential equation of the bent line will be:

$$EJ \frac{d^2 S_{\partial y}}{dx^2} + \Delta Q_{ox} S_{\partial y} \frac{d^2 S_{\partial y}}{dx^2} = -\Delta Q_{ox} \frac{d^2 f_{\partial y}}{dx^2} \quad (8)$$

If we integrate equation (8) twice, we get:

$$EJ \frac{d^2 \sigma_{\partial y}}{dx^2} + \Delta Q_{ox} f_{\partial y} = -\Delta Q_{ox} \cdot S_0 + A' + B'x \quad (9)$$

The general solution of this equation is sought as follows:

$$S_{\partial y} = C \sin kx + D \cos kx + A' + Bx + f_{\partial y} \quad (10)$$

here

$$k = \sqrt{\frac{\Delta Q_{0x}}{FJ}} \quad (11)$$

Let's define the solution of the equation for the special case as follows:

$$f_y = A'' + B'' \cos \frac{2\pi X}{l_{pak}} \quad (12)$$

Just like that

$$\begin{aligned} 4EJB'' \frac{\pi^2}{l_{fil}^2} \cdot \cos \frac{2\pi x}{L_{pak}} + \Delta Q_{ox} A'' + B'' \Delta Q_{ox} \cos^2 \frac{2\pi x}{l_{fil}} = \\ = -\frac{\Delta Q_{ox} f_0}{2} \cdot \left(1 + \cos \frac{2\pi x}{l_{fil}} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

here

$$\begin{aligned} A'' = -\frac{f_0}{2} \\ B'' = \frac{\Delta Q_{ox}}{2 \left(4EJ \frac{\pi^2}{l_{fil}^2} - \Delta P_{ox} \right)} = \frac{f_0}{2 \left(\frac{P_{kp}}{\Delta Q_{\alpha}} - 1 \right)} \end{aligned}$$

Now the particular solution can become:

$$S_{\partial y} = \frac{f_0}{2(P_{kr} / \Delta Q_{ox} - 1)} - \frac{f_0}{2} \quad (14)$$

Then the general solution of equation (7):

$$S_{ay} = C \sin kx + D \cos kx + A + BX + \frac{f_0 \cos \frac{2\pi x}{L_{pak}}}{2(P_{kr} / \Delta Q_{ox} - 1)} - \frac{f_0}{2} \quad (15)$$

Figure 1. Deformation of the zone of the belt close to the filter

$$2D \cos \frac{kl}{2} + 2A - f_0 - \frac{f_0}{P_{kr} / \Delta Q_{ox} - 1} = 0$$

$$2C \sin \frac{kl}{2} + Bl = 0 \quad (17)$$

$$2Ck \cos \frac{kl}{2} = 0$$

$$2Dk \sin \frac{l}{2} = 0$$

Here, l is the length of the lower nonporous horizon.

(17) we get from Eqs

$$A = \frac{f_0}{2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{(P_{kr} / \Delta Q_{ox} - 1)} \right) \quad (18)$$

$$B=C=D=0$$

Then from equation (15) we get as a final result:

$$S_{ay} = \frac{f_0}{2(P_{kr} / \Delta Q_{ox} - 1)} \left(1 + \cos \frac{2\pi x}{l_{fil}} \right) \quad (19)$$

We can also set the function Δf_{ay} value of the additional dress:

$$\Delta f = \frac{f_0}{(P_{kr} / \Delta Q_{ox} - 1)} \Delta f_{ay} \quad (20)$$

Then the full deflection of the pipes:

$$f_1 = f_0 + \Delta f_{ay} \quad (21)$$

$$\Delta f_{1cy} = \frac{f_0}{(1 - \Delta Q_{ox} / P_{kr})}$$

here

$$\Delta Q_{ox} = P_{kr} \left(1 - \frac{f_0}{f_1}\right) \quad (22)$$

Bending moment from compressive force

$$M = EJ \frac{d^2 f_{cy}}{dx^2} = -\frac{P_{kr} \cdot Q_{ox} \cdot f_0}{2(P_{kr} - \Delta Q_{ox})} \cos \frac{2\pi x}{l_{fil}} \quad (23)$$

$M = \psi(x)$ and let's determine the extreme values of this function.

$$\frac{d\varphi}{dx} = 0 \quad \text{Sin} 2\pi x / L_{pak} = 0 \quad (24)$$

here $x=0$, $x = \pm l_{fil}/2$

So, the destructive moment reaches its extreme value at three points at the destructive values of the load:
 $x = l_{fil}/2$; $x = -l_{fil}/2$ və mütləq qiyməti

$$M = \left| \frac{\Delta Q_{ox} \cdot P_{kr} f_0}{2(P_{kr} - \Delta Q_{ox})} \right| \quad (25)$$

Extreme value of stress from axial bending loads

$$\sigma_{max} = \frac{\Delta Q_{ox}}{F} + \frac{M}{W} \quad (26)$$

Here W is the moment of resistance

$$W = \pi D^2 \delta_{boru} / 4$$

here

$$\Delta Q_{ox} = \frac{P_{kr} + \sigma_{ax} F + \frac{P_{kr} f_0 \cdot F}{2W}}{2} - \sqrt{\frac{(P_{kr} + \sigma_{ax} F + \frac{P_{kr} f_0 \cdot F}{2W})^2}{4} \cdot P_{kr} \cdot \sigma_{ax} \cdot F} \quad (27)$$

Then we can determine the moment depending on the slope f_1 - as follows:

$$M = \pm \Delta Q_{ox} \frac{f_1}{2} \quad (28)$$

From the joint solution of equations (20) and (21), taking into account (25)-5, we determine:

$$f_1 = \frac{\frac{2W}{F} - f_0 - \frac{2W \cdot \sigma_{S(ax)}}{P_{kr}}}{2} - \sqrt{\left(\frac{2W}{F} - f_0 - \frac{2W \sigma_{S(ax)}}{P_{kr}}\right)^2 + \frac{2W f_0}{F}} \quad (29)$$

(21) and (22) for packer tubes ($\varnothing 73$ mm) (thickness 7 mm),

$E = 2,1 \cdot 10^5$ MPa, $\sigma_{ax} = 380$ MPa, $f_0 = 3 \cdot 10^{-2}$ m the prices of calculation in prices: $P_{kr} = 4\pi^2 EJ / l_{fil}$:
 $kq - 27300 \Delta Q_{ok}$, $kq - 24150$, (2) f_1 , mm (28)-256 will be.

CONCLUSION

In order to carry out certain repair works in the filter zone in wells, when the belt near the filter is tightened with a packer, since the pump-compressor pipes are connected to the packer, an axial bending occurs in the pipes.

References

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